

Lab tips, tricks and hacks:

Simple vacuum probe station for optoelectronic measurements

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We present a home-built vacuum probe station designed for optoelectronic measurements. An overview sketch of the system can be found below. We use a big feedthrough collar and equip it with a magnetic table that can hold four custom built probes on micromanipulator stages. Electrical access to the chamber is provided by BNC connectors. Optical access is provided by a borosilicate window in the lid of the chamber. A fiber-coupled tube lens allows sample illumination with any fiber-coupled light source.

Figure 1. Sketch of the setup. A big chamber is equipped with a magnetic table that holds the sample stage. Home-built probe tips are connected to BNC connectors. A window in the lid gives optical access to the sample, using a fiber-coupled tube lens system.

Chamber hardware

Table 1. Summary of the components needed for the assembly of the simple vacuum probe station. (Prices and links are from 2020 when the system was assembled).

Vendor	Quantity	Part number	Description	Unit price	Subtotal
Lesker	1	FT1208SU	Feedthrough collar	2650	2650
	1	BP1200SUA	Top plate	560	560
	1	BP1200SUO	Bottom plate	1305	1305
	1	O-V454	O-ring bottom plate	65.4	65.4
Hositrاد	1	CF100/B	Flange 6"	69	69
	1	VG100	Gasket 6"	15	15
	1	HVP-ISO100	Viewport	195	195
	1	ISO100AV	Centering ring for viewport	16.5	16.5
	6	ISO63/CG	ISO Clamp for viewport	2.5	15
	2	7184-06-CF	BNC feedthrough	279	558
	1	CFA35/KF25	Adaptor CF to KF (for pumping)	42	42
	3	CF35/B	Blank CF flange	14	42
Thorlabs	1	10583-01-CF	Thermocouple feedthrough	176	176
	1	V2L6S	Optical fiber feedthrough	453.63	453.63
Amazon	1	Haljia R=10	Ceramic metal heater (sample stage)	13.66	13.66
	2	MAGN	Magnets (set of 15)	7.15	14.30
Aliexpress	2	MAXYZ40R	XYZ manual stage (right handed)	91.73	183.46
	2	MAXYZ40L	XYZ manual stage (left handed)	91.73	183.46
Ebay	1	P50B1	0.48mm Diameter Spring Loaded Probe Pin (x98)	12.37	12.37
Total					6569.78

Figure 2. Pictures of the system before and after closing the chamber.

Home-built parts for the vacuum chamber

The vacuum chamber has to be supplemented with 4 supports to rest the chamber onto the optical breadboard.

Figure 3. Detail of a home-built support post screwed on the vacuum chamber bottom plate (BP1200SUO).

Probes:

Spring-loaded tips are soldered onto the probe arms for electrical connection with coaxial cables. Soldered pins at the end of the cable allow for quick plug-connection to the BNC connectors of the chamber.

Figure 4. (left) Picture of one of the XYZ probe micro-manipulator stages. (right) Detail of the PCB board with the spring-loaded tip (that will be used as electrical probe) soldered at the end and the connection to a coaxial cable.

Figure 5. (left) The sample stage and the XYZ probe micro-manipulator stages are mounted on a home-built magnetic table. (right) Picture of the table and the stages located inside the vacuum chamber. The magnetic table ensures that the sample and probes are at an appropriate height to inspect them with the zoom lens imaging system.

Figure 6. Pictures of the system before and after closing the chamber. A light source is fiber-coupled to the tube lens for vertical illumination of the sample inside of the chamber.

Heater stage:

A ceramic heater mounted onto the sample stage enables in-situ annealing and temperature-dependent measurements (from room temperature to $\sim 300^{\circ}\text{C}$). A thermocouple, connected to one of the BNC connectors, allows to track temperature in real time.

Figure 7. Heating element on the sample stage.

Optical inspection system

Table 2. Summary of the optical components needed for the assembly of the inspection system. (Prices and links are from 2020 when the system was assembled).

Vendor	Quantity	Part number	Description	Unit price	Subtotal
AMScope	1	SKU: DAW-B	Heavy Duty Double-Arm Black Boom Stand	226.99	226.99
Aliexpress	1	ZOOM LENS	400x zoom lens with coaxial illuminator	185.99	185.99
	1	DIGI CAM	21 MPix HDMI + USB camera	77.88	77.88
Total					490.86

Home-built parts for the optical inspection system

The AMScope double-arm boom stand (SKU:DAW-B) comes with a focusing stage for 76 mm diameter optical systems while the 400x zoom lens with coaxial illuminator is built to be mounted in 50 mm diameter focusing stages. Therefore, an adaptor part has to be machined in the workshop:

Figure 8. Sketch (not at scale) of the home-built part to adapt the 400x zoom lens to the boom stand focusing stage.

Also, in our case we mounted the whole system in a passively damped optical breadboard and in order to fix the boom stand to the optical breadboard we needed to machine a home-built part:

Figure 10: Detail of the home-built parts employed in the optical inspection system.

The system can be equipped with any pumping station. In our case we use a T-Station T85 from Edwards, consisting of a rough pump and a turbo pump. The evolution of the chamber pressure is shown below.

Figure 11. Evolution of the pressure in the vacuum chamber as a function of time upon pumping with a turbo pump station system.